

Conceptualisation and description of a real-time processor SW for daytime/nighttime Brewer retrievals

1. Introduction

This document outlines a potential real-time implementation of the algorithm for ozone and nitrogen dioxide retrievals, both during the day and night, from the MkIV Brewer spectrophotometer operating at the BAQUNIN site (Sapienza – University of Rome).

Due to ownership-related questions concerning the Brewer data, the real-time processor has not yet been implemented. Once these formal matters are resolved, and the responsible personnel at Sapienza university are identified for the implementation, the processor will be shortly put in operation.

2. Overall software architecture

The overall architecture of the real-time processor has been designed to accommodate the rapid development and updating of the methodology for retrieving nitrogen dioxide during both the day and night, as well as for the one to retrieve ozone at night, by ARPA Valle d'Aosta. Hence, to facilitate modifications and bug fixes, the data will be transmitted to ARPA's server for processing.

A schematic representation is provided in Fig. 1. It includes:

- **Saving of the raw data** after measurement on a PC at Sapienza University.
- **Data transmission module** that sends the raw data to ARPA's FTP server at regular intervals (e.g., hourly). An account on the server has already been activated for this purpose.
- **Crontab script** for **downloading** the data from the FTP server onto the processing server (Linux).
- **Set of R scripts to retrieve** ozone and nitrogen dioxide.
- **Software maintenance and updates** will be regularly performed by ARPA.
- **Cronjob** that **sends** the retrieved concentrations back to Sapienza University after processing.

Once data are received at Sapienza University, the local personnel will be responsible for publishing them and further forwarding them to the relevant databases.

As a technical remark, the data file volume is expected to be a few kilobytes, which will not significantly impact the server's traffic or pose any technical issue.

Fig. 1: Conceptual scheme of the real-time processor for NO₂ and O₃ Brewer retrievals.